

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS

Egamberdiyeva Umida

Student of Tashkent state University of Uzbek language and literature named after Alisher Navai

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8027687>

Abstract. *The current research attempts to determine whether teaching speaking to foreign language learners using real materials is successful. Participants in this study were a group of intermediate-level language students from language centers who, on average, ranged in age from 14 to 17 years old. Participants received two additional speaking lessons to achieve results. During the first lesson, a group of students was instructed and engaged in exercises using customary and unauthentic materials. We noticed their activity and interest. Participants in the second meeting were also watched. However, the fact that they were taught using real materials made the difference between the two lessons. When teaching speaking, using authentic materials is more effective than using standard course materials, according to both observation and results.*

Keywords: *authentic materials, teaching speaking, speaking skills.*

Introduction

Speaking is an interactive process in which the listener shares and processes the information as necessary. In order to communicate successfully, it is crucial to acquire both speaking and listening abilities. It is an essential component of learning and a productive or expressive speech talent. Speaking is the act of using spoken language to communicate ideas and emotions. Informing others through speech is common. Speaking abilities help each kid in the classroom to ask questions, give information, and assess understanding. The classroom is the most crucial setting for teaching kids how to communicate their ideas and listen to others. Additionally, instructional materials are crucial for language learning.

There are two categories of teaching materials: authentic and non-authentic. Both types of materials have an effect on learners' assimilation when used to teach speaking. Students can be inspired and made comfortable using a foreign language by using authentic materials in the classroom. Despite not being created specifically for language teaching, authentic materials can be put to a variety of uses when used properly in authentic learning environments. As a result, in a constructivist learning environment, foreign language teachers must expose their pupils to real materials.

Literature review

For teaching speaking English as a foreign language, teachers and students find authentic materials to be a useful tool. One of the most crucial skills for EFL learners to communicate with others is speaking. Non-native English speakers can help professors show their pupils how the language is used outside of the classroom by incorporating them into speaking classes.

Teaching speaking

Despite the importance of speaking in a second language, there are few recent studies devoted to language teaching, with the exception of Boxer and Cohen (2004), Bygate (2000), Bygate, Skehan and Swain (2001) and Ellis (2005). In second language teaching, speaking is a demanding skill, as Brown (1994) described production with phenomena such as vowel reduction and elision good difficult spoken language. Lazaraton (2001) also considers that elements such as

slang and idioms make speaking a difficult skill to learn, not to mention stress and pace and intonation. Bygate (1987) considers speech to be an undervalued ability. Because people have the ability to speak is taken for granted in a first language, while writing skills will always require training, which will cause them to be overestimated. However, speaking a second language also requires specific training as it is different and more complicated process that requires the speaker to encode a message and then decode it part of the listener. The qualities of the spoken language must also be taken into account in class.

This ability can be broken down into three main areas that are commonly associated with success: fluidity, complexity and accuracy. In fact, complexity and precision are closely related to the construction of familiarity. This last term is used by Segalowitz (2003: 384) as an "Ability in the second language to produce or understand utterances fluently, quickly and fluently accurate". Speed of delivery is associated with the ability to produce linguistic structures, and Bygate (2009) distinguishes between speed and regularity, which refers to the amount and organization of breaks. In turn, Skehan and Foster (2005) identify two keys. Elements of Fluid: Disturbance Fluid and Repair Fluid, the former referring to breaks focused on "creating treatment time supplements" (Bygate, 2009: 10) and the latter are those interruptions that occur when the speaker corrects "phrasing problems" and "articulation" (Bygate, 2009: 10). Teachers should pay attention to accuracy and fluency, and should understand fluency not only as the ability to link linguistic elements, but also as "use of natural language" in the sense of Hedge (1993). As we can see if the type of speaking is interactive, this skill has not always been at the heart of second language teaching methodology and it is also important that precision and fluidity are considered as ways to promote language usage.

What is authentic material?

In the literature, terminologies of authentic materials have been defined in various ways. According to Martinez (2002) and Hwang (2005), authentic documents (written or spoken) are those intended for native English speakers, not language students. Whereas Kilickaya (2004) defined authentic materials as the disclosure of real language and its use in their real community. This type of material includes many aspects such as cultural components (expressions, idioms, and jargon) as well as how the language is used by native speakers in their context. Following this logic, Gebhard (1996) classified authentic documents as follows: 1) authentic audio and visual documents: television commercials, quizzes, cartoons, news clips, comedy shows, films, soap operas, short stories, and professionally recorded novels, radio commercials, songs, documentaries, and sales pitches. 2) authentic visual materials: slides, photographs, paintings, children's artwork, stick figure drawings, wordless road signs, silhouettes, magazine images, ink blots, postcard images, picture books without words, postage stamps, and xrays. 3) authentic printed materials: newspaper articles, movie advertisements, astrology columns, sports reports, obituaries, advice columns, song lyrics, restaurant menus, street signs, cereal boxes, candy wrappers, brochures tourist information, university catalogs, telephone directories, maps, television programs, comic books, greeting cards, grocery coupons, news pins, and bus schedules. Some have attested to the positive effects of using authentic materials. Kilickaya (2004) found that authentic texts give students the feeling of learning an authentic and realistic language. Another empirical evidence was also provided by Gilmore (2007: 111). He compared the influence of authentic material versus textbook material on the development of communicative competence of students in the experimental group in a one-year experimental study at a Japanese university and

found that students who received the authentic inputs made statistically significant progress compared with the control group on six trials designed to measure different types of proficiency.

Speaking authentic materials

As it was mentioned, in order to transmit information to native speakers and not for educational purposes, authentic materials are those that are produced for that purpose. Here there are some examples of speaking authentic materials

- a) Articles from newspapers, magazines and journals
- b) Radio and television scripts and documentaries, shows, news segments, movie clips, online videos and commercials
- c) Comic books for entertainment, blogs, social media posts
- d) Publicity brochures and posters, postcards, street signs, maps
- e) Short stories, poems and plays
- f) Photographs, picture stories

Using authentic materials to teach speaking

Considering the complexity of speaking by using English as a foreign language (EFL), EFL teachers, therefore, do need to understand well how to facilitate their students to be able to communicate by using the target language. To enable the EFL teachers to facilitate learning, there are some principles teachers need to bear in mind when they intend to obtain such goals; amongst them are understanding students' psychology, classroom management, selecting suitable teaching strategies and media as well as teaching materials. Focusing on teaching speaking (Brown,2007:331) highlights that one of the principles EFL teachers need to hold in teaching speaking is putting up authentic language during teaching. Therefore, to be able to provide authentic language, teachers need to give their students authentic materials. Discussing authentic materials, some definitions have already been uttered by experts such as Dascalos and Ling (2005: 11); claim that authentic materials refer to the language used in society's daily life and is not meant for pedagogical communication. Talking about non-pedagogical communication in authentic material domain, Belaid, and Murray (2015: 16) put it as the appropriateness of the materials with the student's needs and the learning objectives. The two given definitions, lead us to an insight that, in the language-teaching field, authentic material is that any written and spoken language that the students hear, see, and use in their daily life; the language is not meant for educational purposes but still can be so beneficial in the teaching and learning language process. Some benefits of using authentic materials they contribute a positive effect on student motivation; provide students with information about the real culture of the target language; expose students to real language; relate more closely to students' needs, and support more creative approach to teaching (Berardo, 2006: 64). Further Harmer (1994 in Al Azri and Al-Rashdi, 2016: 252) state that authentic materials have a good impact on language learners because they can assist learners to produce better language output; help learners acquire the target language, and boost students' confidence to deal with the language used in real life. Many researchers have done it on purpose of learning usage of a real material. However, the research emphasis is placed on the effectiveness of original materials and the use of genuine materials. Improving students' language skills; for example, Idayani Hartatik and Rahma's study, a study of students' attitudes towards authentic materials. After conducting Classroom Action Research, he found that the original material successfully improved the speaking skills of 10th grade students at SMA Nurul Falah in Pekanbaru, Indonesia. He also found that real-life materials could boost students' confidence and motivation. Efficiency of use,

unlike Indrayani (2014) and Rasheed (2014) Practical Speaking Material for Malaysian EFL Students; his latest finding showed that students achieved much better results after being taught using real materials because real materials can stimulate and enrich the language learning experience of the experimental group. In addition to the above studies, several studies were conducted that elicited student perspectives. Firmansyah (2015) did one. His results showed that students taught with real material perceived the real material as interesting (ensuring that they enjoyed the lesson), challenging (increased interest in learning) and motivation (active participation in class).

It is obvious that the use of authentic materials in language teaching is supported by many researchers. They consider the usage of this kind of materials as a helpful way to pique students' interest and motivate them. However, some researchers are opposed to using authentic materials. They don't want to use classroom resources because they think they might be too culturally specific biased and have difficult language and structure. This might aggravate students in spite of the benefits of teaching students with authentic materials although this is unfavorable perception. As many researchers work have been learned, in this course paper another work is researched on using authentic materials to teach speaking.

Methodology

Research design

In order to determine whether real resources are more effective for language learners, this qualitative study report is centered on employing authentic materials to teach speaking. A group of participants on the intermediate level who attend language centers participated in the study over the course of two days (two courses). Students' activity in both meetings was observed during the investigation. The study's goal was to examine how real materials affected students' speaking abilities and their development. Participants were instructed using customary, non-authentic materials on the first day, then authentic materials on the following day. Both lessons were prepared a day in advance, and for the second lesson, a TV movie about friendship was selected as authentic content. Both lessons were controlled, analyzed and taken some important notes for observation. After that, results were compared.

Participants

A total of 12 students from a language center intermediate level course participated in the current study. They ranged in age from 14 to 17 on average, with four of them being male and eight of them being female students. All participants were on an equal footing, but some male students spoke less frequently than female students. The students have never lived overseas.

Procedure

On the first day I went to the language center and I came into a group which I should take a research. Almost all participants were there, but one of them came late. I started lesson with greeting and introducing myself. Then I asked about themselves and they also introduced. Female participants tried to speak a lot. After introduction I told them a lesson topic. The topic was chosen a day before and it was about Friendship. Friends are considered important part of our life, that's why this topic was chosen in order to make relevant to authenticity. After giving the topic, I asked participant some question related to it, such as What is friendship? How important is friend in our life? How is ideal friend for you? and so on. Students tried to answer with their own opinions. Female students participated more actively than male students. After their answers, I distributed handouts, a small about friendship was written on them. I gave a task them to read the text and

retell it. After they have finished reading, I started to ask them retelling one-by-one. Again, female participants answered a lot. Then I asked them bring a photo that they had taken with their friends for the next lesson as a homework. For the second lesson everyone came on time and I realized that all of them brought photos which I asked. We greeted and I asked if they have done the task which I told. All of them were ready. Then I asked them describe a photo that have brought with themselves one-by-one. All participants described their own photo. After that activity, I play a short film about friendship and I asked them to take some notes, and write new words. After watching the film, I told that they should retell the film or tell what they have understood. And also I asked if they had come across any strange word. All participants answered and gave their own opinion. End of the lesson I asked participant about both lessons, their difference and method, they gave feedbacks orally and I took some notes.

Result

During both lesson, I tried to observe all participants and made some important notes. In the first lesson students were not so active. When I had asked their opinion about the first lesson, they answered it was a little bit boring although the topic was interesting. Because they just read a text and answered question. However, the following lesson was interesting and useful for their speaking skill, according to them. The theme was the same, but materials were different. They use authentic (real) materials that they may face on real life. When they were describing photos they had an interest for speaking, they wanted to speak a lot. Also, all participants watched the short movie with deep attention and desire. They could explain own ideas more freely and fluently after watching it than reading a text a day before. They told that they also had learnt new words from the movie. The second day, male participants were more active, even one of them told that some event and episodes of the film were happened in his life, so he could explain his opinion freely. During the research, I noticed that the second lesson with authentic materials, helped students to broaden their horizon. When they had watched the movie I asked them what would they do if they had been instead of the film characters. With watching the movie, they could imagine themselves in situation of it, so they use their outlook and tried to solve problems.

Discussion

The main objective of this research was to know if authentic are efficient on teaching speaking. After the research, results showed that teaching materials have a big impact on any language skills. The theme of lessons was the same, but used materials were different. When teacher used non-authentic materials, students were passive and they got bored, but in the lesson with authentic materials (personal photo, short movie) they were active and tried to speak, answer, give own opinions. By watching the film, they also learnt new words. Meanwhile, there had been many new words on the text they read before, but they had not paid attention to them as they considered it boring. As many researchers have discussed, authentic materials give more efficiency on teaching language with motivating learners.

Recommendation

In order to provide examples of future foreign language teachers using real materials in their own classes, it is necessary to create a learning environment using real materials when training future foreign language teachers. In this way, teachers to-be are given the opportunity to see and experience first-hand the benefits and caveats of these materials. The purpose of this study is to focus on the importance and use of authentic materials in foreign language education and to make some suggestions in this regard. Materials are important as a means of helping teachers to

understand and apply the theories of language learning, and this importance means that they have become a focus of study in their own right. A teacher should have some creative ideas in designing teaching materials. Authentic materials come in different forms, newspaper and magazine articles for example, poems and short stories etc. But in addition to these print based authentic materials, the rapid development of computer technology. Authored materials refer to textbooks and other specially designed materials. Real material is different from another material. It was developed by teachers who recognized the important role technology plays in teaching and learning. This case becomes interesting when integrated into teaching and learning. Teachers coordinate the functions of technology in the learning process. Therefore, when teaching speaking using authentic materials, English teachers need to find ways to enable students to practice and communicate in their own English. A good teacher's speech activity can and should be very engaging for students. Students who understand each other well and have sufficient English skills. At the right level and given right topic by the teacher, they are often free and enthusiastic to participate and to do tasks.

Conclusion

After researching the relevant literature, it becomes evident that many researchers strongly favor the use of real materials in language training. They believe that using these resources in the classroom is a powerful method to motivate pupils, stimulate their interest, and expose them to language they will use in everyday life. Authentic resources also assist language learners in their learning process because they enable them to visualize themselves using the language in real-world contexts. Using authentic resources, in the opinion of some experts, makes language learners feel as though they are studying the "real" language, which encourages them to acquire it. Furthermore, it is asserted that one of the key advantages of using authentic materials is that it enhances students' motivation and has an impact on their learning process. Because authentic materials may be too culturally biased and have complex wording and structures, some researchers are opposed to using them in the classroom. Children in schools could become upset by this. Despite this bad view, some studies have demonstrated that the benefits of utilizing real materials when teaching ESL students outweigh the disadvantages, and this makes using authentic materials while teaching ESL students an essential method that EFL teachers should employ to help their students' language learning. The results of a study conducted by a different researcher provide additional proof that employing authentic materials is "more effective than using non-authentic materials". The researchers hold this view, and it is unquestionably the important role that such real materials have played and will continue to play in the effective, worthwhile learning process that must take place in every teacher's classroom. Furthermore, I learned from my research and from the results of my students that authentic materials are a significant help when learning a language. Due to speaking exercises and activities involving real materials, students' interest and engagement increased throughout the course.

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